

STUDY OF PRESUPPOSITION IN UZBEK VERBS

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Azamat Mehmonaliyevich Toshpo'latov

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute,

Associate Professor of

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqola fe'l turkumi doirasida pressupozitsiya hodisasi yuzaga kelishga doir kuzatishlarga bag'ishlangan. Bu borada jahon tilshunoslarining ilmiy qarashlari tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar:

pragmatika, pressupozitsiya, muloqot atvori, ijtimoiy omil, til birligi bahosi.

Annotatsiya:

Dannaya statya posvyashena nablyudeniyam za vozniknoveniem sobytiya pressupozitsii v ryadu glagolov. Analiziruyutsya nauchnye vzglyady mirovyykh yazykovedov na etot schet.

Ключевые слова:

pragmatika, pressupozitsii, povedenie obsheniya, sotsialnyy faktor, otsenka yazykovoy yedinity

Annotation:

This article focuses on observations of the occurrence of a presupposition event within a series of verbs. The scientific views of world linguists on this area are analyzed.

Key words:

Pragmatics, presupposition, communication skill, social factor, language unit value.

Currently, the only definition of a proposition in linguistics is the objective content expressed in the semantics of a sentence⁷⁶. It is known that a proposition is expressed through a syntactic structure of different levels: through a sentence, through turns, even some words and grammatical forms in a simple sentence can express a separate proposition and make this simple sentence semantically complex. In this case, the proposition expressed by some word or grammatical

⁷⁶ Ҳақимов М. Ўзбек прагмалингвистикаси асослари. – Т.: Akademnashr, 2013. – Б. 43.

form will have its most compact form. Presupposition helps to make it understandable for the speaker and the listener. Therefore, the presupposition side of the sentence attracts more attention of linguists in the later periods⁷⁷. Nevertheless, the presupposition is interpreted differently.

The concept of presupposition is related to the ideas of the German logician G. Frege. He stated that presupposition is the natural basis of judgment. For example, in the sentences "Kepler died in poverty" and "Kepler did not die in poverty" there is a natural basis for the judgment that a person named "Kepler" lived. According to G. Frege, the main judgment is often accompanied by another hidden judgment. It presupposes only the implicit second-order judgment of existence⁷⁸.

E. Kenin recommends dividing into practical and logical presuppositions. The first is the structure of individual knowledge of the speaker, and the second is reflected in the semantic relationship between sentences⁷⁹.

L. M. Vasiliev divides meaning components into mandatory and facultative (potential) meaning components according to the degree of connection to a certain meaning. The first of them refers to the significant (semantic) aspect of meaning and is absolutely necessary for its existence as a linguistic unit, while the second refers to the denotative aspect - the plan of presupposition, and this component shows that presupposition is understood only in speech⁸⁰.

According to the scientist, facultative components expand the semiotic possibilities of meaning. For example, in the meaning of the construction "reported", there are facultative components that can be expressed by verbs such as tell, write, call, send a telegram. In the above construction, which method of communication is used, the presupposition plan is known only through the practical knowledge of the language of the speakers.

The use of the term "presupposition" in linguistics is associated with the name of P. Strawson. It shows that language has a special kind of implication. This type of implication is interpreted very close to G. Frege's "natural basis". Both authors

⁷⁷ Арутюнова Н. Д. Понятие презумпции в лингвистической семантике / Семантика и информатика. – М., 1977. – №8.; Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая организация предложения. – Л., 1977. – С. 135.; Гак В.Г. Теоретическая грамматика французского языка. Синтаксис. – М., 1981. – С. 14.; Крейдлин Г.Е. Лексема «даже» / Семантика и информатика. – М., 1975. – №6.; Торопова Н. А. К исследованию логических частиц / ВЯ. 1978. – №5.; Махмудов Н. Прессупозиция ва гап / Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Т., 1986. – №6.; Нурмонов А. Ўзбек тилида кўмакчили конструкциялар прессупозицияси / Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Т., 1986. – №6 ва бошқалар.

⁷⁸ Семантика и информатика. – М., 1977. – №8.

⁷⁹ Бу ҳақда қаранг: Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая предложения. – Л., 1977. – С. 135-138.

⁸⁰ Васильев Л. М. Семантика русского глагола. – М., 1981. – С. 25.

derive the presupposition from the semantic relationship between sentences. This relationship is expressed by the formula "X requires Y". The construction "Mary cleaned the room" contains the presupposition "the room is dirty". This presupposition is also preserved in the construction "Mary did not clean the room"⁸¹.

Nowadays, presupposition is defined as a "common fund of knowledge", "a sum of prior knowledge" between the speakers, which allows for the correct understanding of a certain sentence and the proposition it represents⁸².

Therefore, in linguistics, the term presupposition refers to a meaning that is not directly expressed in a certain sentence, but is secretly reflected.

The concept of presupposition includes the concepts of context (the linguistic environment of this language unit) and situation (the extralinguistic substrate of this sentence, the conditions for its occurrence)⁸³. For example, the information in the sentence Today I left our instructor, dad (A. Qahhor) is related to the context. "Chess", the subject of information, is known from the context. The sentence in the previous sentence is about chess, so the sentence above has the presupposition "I played chess with our instructor." Out of context, the way is closed for presupposition.

As a result of people's universal knowledge of the world around them and language skills, the way to presupposition can be opened in the lexical meanings of some words. For example, the sentence "I flew from Tashkent to Samarkand" contains the presupposition "I arrived by plane". The lexical meaning of the word "I flew" and the general knowledge of the language open the way for speakers to presuppose.

Linguistic presupposition, unlike logical presupposition, has a certain form of expression - material means, external signals. For example, in the sentence Karim also came, the presupposition someone else came. The material substrate of this presupposition is the external signal "also" loading.

Because this loading paves the way for presupposition. Also, the means of coming to the surface (on foot, by car, on horseback, etc.) is known through presupposition.

As a material substrate of presupposition in the Uzbek language, various means can participate: 1) facultative meaning components of lexical means; 2) prepositions even, only, alone, -gina (not -gina), also, tagin, again; 3) if there is, then

⁸¹ Торопова Н. А. К исследованию логических частиц / ВЯ. – М., 1977. – С. 83.

⁸² Гак В. Г. Теоретическая грамматика французского языка. Синтаксис. – М., 1981. – С. 14.

⁸³ Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая организация предложения. – Л., 1977. – С. 137

connecting means; 4) besides, other, other (Besides you, Karim also came), with, together with (He was smart as well as being beautiful), instead of (He plays instead of studying) assistants and etc.

Presupposition is inextricably linked with the meaning aspect of syntactic constructions.

V. V. Bogdanov emphasizes that presupposition is an aspect of sentence semantics⁸⁴. N. D. Arutyunova also shows that the presupposition enters the semantics of the sentence as a "general fund of knowledge of the speakers", "their prior agreement"⁸⁵. In further studies, pragmatics is separated from semantics, and presupposition is included in pragmatics.

Researchers classify presupposition in different ways. In particular, V. G. Gak shows the following types of presupposition: 1) broad presupposition; 2) narrow presupposition; 3) linguistic presupposition.

Under the broad presupposition is understood the universal knowledge of people about the objective reality that surrounds them. Each object in the objective existence has a typical, characteristic feature, adaptation to a known thing. When describing such characteristics of objects, a word with a concrete meaning can be replaced by a more general word or completely omitted. But for the speaker and the listener to understand each other correctly, its omission does not play any role. For example, when talking about a chauffeur, the speaker and the listener, first of all, think of him as a car driver. Therefore, although the word car is omitted in the sentence "The driver drove the car fast", it does not spoil the meaning.

A narrow presupposition means a presupposition that occurs only within a certain situation. A presupposition resulting from the experience of speakers of this language is a linguistic presupposition.

E. V. Paducheva shows two types of presupposition (presumption): 1) semantic presupposition is a semantic component whose falsity leads to semantic falsity of the sentence; 2) pragmatic presumption is such a component of the sentence that the speaker believes is known to the listener in its normal use.

N. A. Toropova also divides presupposition into two groups: 1) presupposition of conflicting members; 2) expected presupposition.

Thus, until today, there is no clear classification of presupposition, based on one sign, recognized by all. The concept of presupposition is related to the concept of assertion.

⁸⁴ Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая организация предложения. – Л., 1977. – С. 137.

⁸⁵ Арутюнова Н. Д. Понятие презумпции в лингвистической семантике / Семантика и информатика. – М., 1977. – №8. – С. 85.

N.A. Toropova shows that presupposition and assertion differ according to the sign of "certainty-uncertainty". Presupposition is the meaning of the sentence specific to the context, and assertion is the meaning independent of it. For example, the predicate noun artist corresponds to the subjective semantic sign of the presupposition. Compare: There are two statements logically derived from the sentence "here is an artist": 1) there is a person here; 2) this person is a liar.

The semantics of the noun in the analyzed sentence includes classifying and characterizing signs. In the word "artist" (in the sense of a liar, master), the meanings of "person", "older", "man" are classification symbols.

The meaning of "man" in the sentence "man artist" is found in the taxonomic symbol of the word "artist". Therefore, its direct use does not perform a presuppositional function, but an assertive function.

Here, all the semantic components of the noun in the presence clauses of the artist have type are characteristic for the whole sentence. Thus, classification symbols are important for existential information. Its characteristics are valuable for information that characterizes the subject.

The presupposition is connected to a certain extent with the actual division of the sentence. In particular, their connection is manifested through the focus under the logical emphasis in the structure of the syntactic structure.

According to V.V. Bogdanov, if there is a focus in a sentence, it is a rheme at the same time. Under normal conditions, rhema can combine one or more words, and focus reduces them to a minimum. For example, in the sentence I read interesting books, if the word interesting is the focus, it is the rheme, and the other words are the theme. At the same time, the focus is always within the presuppositional influence. In particular, the presupposition that I will not read other books comes from the sentence above, with the logical emphasis on the word interesting.

Other means of actualization: actualization using word order changes, actualization using lexical and grammatical means, etc. are also closely related to presupposition. All this testifies to the complex relationship between the concepts of presupposition and actual division.

Nevertheless, actual division and presupposition have different signs in terms of form and content.

According to V. V. Bogdanov, their formal differences are that presupposition is characterized by the separation of at least two predicate expressions, one of which is hidden inside the other. For example, the predicate expression Karim is building a house contains the predicate expression the house is being built. The

second expression is a presupposition of the first. Actual division components are separated within a predicate expression.

The substantive difference between them is that actual division is intended to separate the known and the new from the structure of the sentence. If the known sentence connects to the previous sentence and serves to create a text, the new sentence advances the meaning of the sentence. The presupposition is not connected with the functional side of the sentence. If the actual structure includes the formal aspect of the sentence, the presupposition does not have this feature.

It is known that the leading morpheme in the word is the base. It has a semantic core, lexical meaning depends on it, and additional morphemes play a secondary role. But this is so at first glance. Professor L. V. Shcherba refers to the following "sentence" to explain to students that not only the base of the word, but also each part is important: "Glokaya kuzdra shteko budlanula bokra i kurdyachit bokryonka" and explains the role and importance of morphemics based on this unusual syntactic device will give. In a "sentence" the "grammatical elements" can be distinguished factually, but there is no presupposition. So, although the actual division of the sentence and presupposition are related phenomena, there are important differences between them in terms of content and form.

I don't like this boy. You will see, one day he will give you a hint. (S. Ahmad, "Silence") presuppositional meanings such as "the child is not trusted, he warned before" are understood by expressing the verb phrase in the future tense.

In conclusion, it is clear that the verb word group is much superior to other word groups with its colorful forms, unlimited pragmatic possibilities, and the ability to change the speech situation, and this situation is new to researchers. - creates new tasks horizontally.

REFERENCES:

1. ҲАКИМОВ М. Ўзбек прагмалингвистикаси асослари. - Т.: Akademnashr, 2013. - Б. 43.
2. Арутюнова Н. Д. Понятие презумпции в лингвистической семантике / Семантика и информатика. - М., 1977. - №8.; Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая организация предложения. - Л., 1977. - С. 135.; Гак В.Г. Теоретическая грамматика французского языка. Синтаксис. - М., 1981. - С. 14.; Крейдлин Г.Е. Лексема «даже» / Семантика и информатика. - М., 1975. - №6.; Торопова Н. А. К исследованию логических частиц / ВЯ. 1978. - №5.; Махмудов Н. Прессупозиция ва гап / Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. - Т., 1986. -

№6.; Нурмонов А. Ўзбек тилида кўмакчили конструкциялар пресупозицияси / Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Т., 1986. – №6 ва бошқалар.

3. Семантика и информатика. – М., 1977. – №8.

4. Бу ҳақда қаранг: Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая предложения. – Л., 1977. – С. 135-138.

5. Васильев Л. М. Семантика русского глагола. – М., 1981. – С. 25.

6. Торопова Н. А. К исследованию логических частиц / ВЯ. – М., 1977. – С. 83.

7. Гак В. Г. Теоретическая грамматика французского языка. Синтаксис. – М., 1981. – С. 14.

8. Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая организация предложения. – Л., 1977. – С. 137

9. Богданов В. В. Семантико-синтаксическая организация предложения. – Л., 1977. – С. 137.

10. Арутюнова Н. Д. Понятие презумпции в лингвистической семантике / Семантика и информатика. – М., 1977. – №8. – С. 85.

11. Oripova, K. (2023). ANTONYMS AS A CULTURAL FACTOR IN ARTISTIC TEXTS INVOLVING SIMILE. *GOSPODARKA I INNOWACJE*.

12. Khanhodjaeva, N. B., & Grabovets, N. V. (2021). Use of New Ecological Methods to Reduce Pesticide Load as Bioprotection against Insect Pests. *Design Engineering*, 3526-3533.

13. Parida, M., Bakhadirovna, B. D., Eshtemirovich, K. U., Mekhmanovich, B. B., & Israilovich, M. G. (2018). Defining of total antioxidants quantity in the leaves of different fruit trees in Uzbekistan territory. *European science review*, (1-2), 19-20.

14. Ханходжыева, N., Ermatova, S. M., Muradova, U. D., & Sadinov, J. S. (2017). АНТРОПОГЕННОЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ ХИМИЧЕСКИХ ВЕЩЕСТВ НА ПОЧВУ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 216-219.

15. Хамдамовна, M. Z., & Daughter, A. G. D. S. (2022). THE ROLE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES, SURPRISING CONNECTIONS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND GERMAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(3), 490-493.

16. Masodiqova, Z. X. (2022). METHODS OF TEACHING GERMAN LANGUAGE. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(1), 331-334.

17. Масодикова, З., & Хатамкулова, Ш. (2021). О'ЗБЕК VA NEMIS MAQOLLARINI QIYOSHLASH. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(1-1).

18. Масодикова, З., & Омонбоева, М. О. (2015). THE EDUCATIONAL IMPORTANCE OF USING PROVERBS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES TEACHING. *Ученый XXI века*, (12 (13)), 73-75.